

Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge, H2020

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5	MiC	MINISTERIO DELLA CULTURA	Italy
6	CNRS	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France
	SORBONNE	SORBONNE UNIVERSITE (LinkedTP)	France
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Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

Research Data Management in Polifonia is a firm part of the overall knowledge management in the project. This third DMP version documents the final status of data management using exclusively the perspective of the **Polifonia Research Ecosystem** approach and its living instance. As for the previous versions of the DMP, we use the template of the Open Research Data (ORDP). While for the first and second version of the DMP we deviated from just given answers to the usual questions, and discussed our approaches to the dimensions of the ORDP, this time we return to the original template in a more rigid way. In particular, in the section FAIR Data we answer all questions using examples from the Polifonia Research Ecosystem to illustrate our response. We add an introduction and conclusion section to the ORDP template.

In the section 1 **Introduction** we point to the specific role of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem approach in managing knowledge exchange and coordination of the knowledge production process in the Polifonia project and introduce into the main structure of the Research Ecosystem. In particular, we detail how the Data type component relates to other major component types such as Tools and Reports. We further illustrate the use of the github based implementation of the Research Ecosystem including the [Polifonia Ecosystem \(v2.0\) website](#), which we recommend to visit next to reading this document.

We continue following the structure of the [Open Research Data Pilot template](#) with its sections: Data Summary; FAIR Data; Allocation of Resources; Data security; Ethical Aspects; Other Aspects.

- **Data summary** describes the final data components of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem. To enable comparison along the various DMP versions we provide (again) in an appendix to this section the updated table of (envisioned) data sources, called "Overview of the main sources used in the pilots".
- **FAIR Data** details all steps to make data FAIR and give examples from the Research Ecosystem, concentrating on Data components which are part of the subtypes Ontology and Knowledge Graph.
- **Allocation of resources** details how in Polifonia FAIRification is not an action to be done after the project, but how it is intrinsic part of the whole research design of the project. We also list here the main webservices and their maintenance strategy.
- **Data Security** we give an overview about the Polifonia Zenodo community
- **Ethical Aspects** we focus on copyright and licensing issues. We detail the practical approach Polifonia has pioneered for FAIR data re-use, and the formalisation steps to include licence issues in machine readable representation of data, described in another deliverable.
- In the section **Other Aspects** we introduce into a survey of re-usability which will be set out in the remaining project time, to further motivate us to increase the impact of the project.

The Polifonia Research Ecosystem will continue to develop, being filled with more components and enriched annotations until the end of the project. There are upcoming deliverables which will detail the technical backbone of the Ecosystem. In this DMP we use the 'now' state of the Ecosystem to check all DMP relevant issues. In this way, writing this DMP is also an evaluation of the use of the Research Ecosystem for DMP purposes.

The DMP closes with a short section 3 **Conclusions** summarising the lessons learned and ideas to transfer the research Ecosystem approach to other collaborative settings. By connecting the lessons learned to the experiences with the Research Ecosystem we point to the possible generic value of such an approach for research data management in open, innovative and interdisciplinary research projects.

Document History

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1. Introduction

Data Management Planning in Polifonia is an intrinsic part of both coordination (of the processes) and documentation (of the results) of the research project. At three points in the timeline of the Polifonia project a Data Management Plan (DMP) in the form of a static document, based on the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) format, is planned as deliverable. The first version of the DMP (2021) [1] documented an inventory of data and introduced into the envisioned methodological approaches to Data Management, most important the Polifonia Research Ecosystem. The second version of the DMP (2022) [2] focused on all formal guidelines Polifonia had developed at this mid-term to ensure FAIR Data management. The central point of this second version was the Rulebook for the Polifonia Research Ecosystem, accompanied by other guidelines around executing Open Science, documenting software, and documenting modules of the Polifonia Knowledge Graph (which constitutes a network of machine readable resources ready for execution of data processing). This third DMP version documents the final status of data management using exclusively the perspective of the Polifonia Ecosystem approach and its living instance. As for the previous versions of the DMP, we use the template of the Open Research Data (ORDP). In section 1 Introduction we point to the specific role of the Polifonia Ecosystem approach in managing knowledge exchange and coordination of the knowledge production process in the Polifonia project. We remind ourselves of essential points of knowledge management in research projects (see section 1.1) and Polifonia's answer to this. We explain how the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP), a template obligatory for EC funded projects, has been applied in the Polifonia context (see section 1.2). This final version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) is based entirely on the now implemented Polifonia Research Ecosystem (see section 1.3). Therefore, in the introduction we introduce the main elements of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem and sketch the timeline of its making.

1.1. Knowledge management in research projects

Research projects with several partners (international and interdisciplinary) require special attention to the management of knowledge exchange inside of the project. European funded projects usually come already with a project management structure taking the form of Work-packages (WP's) and Tasks inside of WP's. To describe their mutual dependencies is part of the Description of Action/Work in any European project proposal. But, research projects by definition are also an excursion into the *unknown*. So, to acknowledge the complex nature of the research process, it is necessary to set up the project planning in a way that it can be adapted. Projects which come with large components of software development require extra means to enable collaborative production of software, and to ensure that the produced components are reusable first for the objectives of the project, and second for re-use by a wider scientific community.

These challenges in projects can be sorted according to three dimensions

- Epistemic: enable mutual understanding between experts from various domains.
- Methodologically: enable exchange of methods and collectively building new methods.
- Documentation: create a system of documentation which serves as a reference base for the project consortium.

As expressed in earlier DMP's [1],[2], Polifonia took specific means from the very beginning to address the complexity of the project objectives. Those means have also been called *SSM*, standing for *Stories* (archotypical user stories), *Survey* (an iterative survey) and *Maninpasta* (targeted workshops and hackatons) [3] [4]. In the course of the project, the Research Ecosystem became the central reference point for all outcomes of Pilots, and (cross-) Workpackage work.

Dimensions	Typical instruments	Polifonia
Epistemic	Meetings, glossary, workshops	Agile working groups/task forces around specific workshops <i>Maninpasta</i> , Socio-technical roadmap(s)
Methodologically	designing schema's of mutual dependencies, milestones and timelines in the Description of Work; choosing platforms for collaborative working	<i>Maninpasta</i> , Definition of <i>pilots</i> as cross-WP connectors, installation of a Technical Board, making working on github obligatory
Documentation	Set of Deliverables, Research Data Management Plan, review of DL's, governance structure as a General Assembly, and a Technical Board	DL's, RDM, GA, TB ... Research Ecosystem approach

Table 1.1: Dimensions and instruments to knowledge management in research projects

1.2. Data management in the Polifonia project - The ORDP template and the various DMP versions

Polifonia is exceptional with respect of the substantial manpower dedicated to data stewardship. Already in the Description of Work this project envisioned a detailed strategy how to document and exchange knowledge inside of the project [5]. That gave data management planning as a part of overall knowledge management a head start. It also created a challenge: namely to use the knowledge management tools which Polifonia envisioned for all kind of internal coordination also for data management. A good example is the iterative survey, which has been used as a tool to develop the Socio-technical Roadmap of the project, to identify the main knowledge units, methodological links between pilots, questions around validation and licensing etc. [4];[3]. Each version of the survey also contained sections with relevant information on data, co-designed by the Data Steward. From the survey(s), main data sources were identified, ordered per pilot, and traced during the duration of the project. The result is documented in the Appendix 1 "Overview of the main sources used in the pilots" in tabular form (see also section 2.1).

As we discussed in the first DMP, each documentation usually serves a specific reason. Existing templates for data management (see Fig.1.1) tend to isolate data from the actual research process. They focus on identifying specific data objects, collections, which can be boxed, defined and described in a reproducible (static) way. But in reality, data are fluid, in change, and so is their description. The Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) balances between the fluid nature of data, by adding to a description of data (Data Summary) several questions (brought together in additional sections) which concern actions undertaken to make data FAIR, ready for re-use and so relates back to all processes around data in a research project.

From the beginning it was not straightforward to match the knowledge organisation behind an ORDP to the actual data management in the project. This is the reason that in the various versions of the DMP, Polifonia embraced the ORDP template in a flexible way. To some extent, the sections of the ORDP were applied to the project as a whole rather than to specific data assets (see Fig 1.2).

One could say that the ORDP template is defined from outside, as part of the science policy boundaries in which funded projects operate. Its sections represent dimensions generally envisioned as to be important. Because of the specific nature of the collaborative work in Polifonia which is essentially interdisciplinary, including collective software engineering, and based on semantic web methodologies, Polifonia designed the so-called Polifonia Research Ecosystem as a means to document and validate all 'research assets'. In the course of the iterations of the DMP, we moved from asking questions towards the project from the perspective of general experiences, as expressed in the ORDP, to giving answers to the making of DMP templates in general based on the experiences of our project. Ultimately, the Polifonia Research Ecosystem as it is developed now, is a template, one could say an **Open Research Component Pilot**, which includes data but also other types of research assets (documented as digital objects and components in a Research Ecosystem).

Steps to improve the DMP (as stated in DMP version 2)	Check at the time of DMP version 3
to check for the good implementation of all rules	rulebook expanded, validator workflow of components designed and tested, workshops around the Ecosystem organised, new FAIR section for all DL's
to explore if those guidelines can be further aligned or even combined	done during Technical Board meetings, workshops and in the population of the Research Ecosystem with components
to monitor where guidelines and rules need to be adapted due to new insights, insights both from the general FAIR discourse as well as from the experiences to work with them in Polifonia	new FAIR section for DL template, Technical Board meetings, Data Steward reviewed all DL's FAIR section
to check if 'score systems' to indicate FAIRness can be implemented	addressed by (a) improving the annotation scheme and (b) designing a validator workflow for the quality of annotations
to use harvesters and overview tools such as the Polifonia Ecosystem website, and the OpenAire explorer to showcase the dynamic output of the project, and to make interlinks and dependencies better visible	New design of the Polifonia Ecosystem website (see this DMP version); link to OpenAire Explorer about Polifonia
to further clarify the situation of around IRP and licences, design a Knowledge Graph of licences	Done, in DL 2.6 "Ontology of licensing, ownership and conditions of use" (submitted, not yet published)

Table 1.2: From DMP version 2 to final version 3

To describe the evolution of the DMP versions, let us shortly summarise them (see also Fig. 1.2). In the DMP version 1, the Polifonia Ecosystem was presented as a design to bring data and others assets together and was complemented by an inventory of the **data assets** of the projects as delivered in the Pilots (Appendix 1 Overview of the main sources used in the pilots). At the time of the DMP version 2, the Polifonia Ecosystem had moved from the blueprint phase to a first implemented version, and so its features were to a large extent documented in the DMP version 2 together with various guidelines which governed knowledge production in the project. For the DMP version 3, we take exclusively the perspective of the Polifonia Ecosystem. We can do so, because all relevant data-related output (such as the Polifonia Ontology, and the Polifonia Knowledge Graph) and all tools/interfaces around them (such as the Polifonia Web portal) are described as components in the Polifonia Research Ecosystem. To present the Polifonia Ecosystem using the ORDP template is, at the same time, a *litmus test* for the ability of the Ecosystem approach to serve as a documentation and monitoring tool. If all aspects of data management, which have been identified due to experiences with large groups of projects (as expressed in the ORDP) are actually also addressed by features of the Polifonia Ecosystem, the test is passed. To further support comparability between the three DMP versions, we again attach an updated *Overview of the main sources used in the pilots* as Appendix. (see Appendix 1). We also add the Polifonia Open Science Rules in the Appendix (Appendix 2).

With the Polifonia Research Ecosystem as our main reference point, we need to introduce some of its features first. However, let us stress here, that while this DMP as a technical document _describes the Ecosystem, we will use one of the upcoming DL's to present the details of its current implementation scientifically. This final DMP describes the content of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem, its components with a special focus on the Data components. Figure 1.3 marks the main steps in the development of the Research Ecosystem.

Figure 1.1: Open Research Data Pilot template

• **DMP Version 1-2-3**

ORDP - section	DMP Version 1	DMP Version 2	DMP Version 3
Data Summary	Data sources description Pilots Co-design of survey	Survey (iterated, extended and data-mined) 2.1.1. Data sources Pilots (updated Table) 2.1.2. Polifonia Data sources as part of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem 2.1.3.	Overview about the Polifonia Ecosystem components of type DATA Cross-links to the Data sources Pilot Table Example of Bell's ontology as a Data component in the Research Ecosystem
FAIR Data	FAIR aspects discussion per Pilot	Polifonia Ontology Network 2.2.1. Polifonia Knowledge Graph 2.2.2. The Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science 2.2.3. FAIR protocol sections 2.2.4. Polifonia Software Guidelines 2.2.5. (including Software deliverable checklist)	Answers to the FAIR question in the ORDP template based on the Research Ecosystem rules Polifonia's approach to FAIR as a process: the new FAIR section in each deliverable
Allocation of Resources	Design of the Polifonia Ecosystem	Polifonia GitHub instance 2.3.1. Implementation of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem 2.3.2. (including Rulebook and Annotation scheme) Polifonia Portal 2.3.3.	Overview about the Polifonia Github instance Outlook to the Polifonia Portal
Data Security	Design of the Polifonia Ecosystem	Polifonia Zenodo community 2.4.1. (including Guidelines)	Overview about the Polifonia Github instance
Ethical Aspects	-	Licences 2.5.	Formalisation and validation of licences as part of the Annotations of Polifonia Ecosystem components
Other Aspects	Awareness raising (webinar)	Polifonia's documentation strategy 2.6.1. Interdependencies of guidelines Overviews as Appendices Updated Table on Pilot sources/ FAIR protocol section (for DL's) / Overview on Licences	Polifonia's approach to encourage reusability and reproducible open science

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Figure 1.2: Comparison of ORDP sections across all three versions of the DMP

Figure 1.3: Timeline of the implementation of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem

1.3. The Polifonia Research Ecosystem

1.3.1. Overview

The Polifonia Research Ecosystem has various parts

- it is a schema – a knowledge organisation system – consisting of types of components and their relationships
- it comes with a *rulebook* including an annotation scheme with metadata for each of the component types
- it is implemented as an instance (repository) in github - connecting to resources in other github repositories
- connected to it is a workflow to validate components and eventually accredit them
- it has an interface (a website build on top of github) which enables to gain an overview, to navigate through components, and to check for their status
- snapshots of the applications constituting it are preserved in the Polifonia Zenodo community; the Polifonia Research Ecosystem website is archived in the Internet Archive

In [6] we describe the motivation and general approach behind the Polifonia Research Ecosystem. In essence, by selecting key research assets (called components) we create a middle layer between the network of knowledge units (as documented in [3],[4] and represented by the pilots and their *Stories*, *Users*, and *Competency questions*); the usual project managements represented in Workpackages and Tasks; and the actual production of (enriched) data and workflows which are documented either as part of the [Polifonia Github instance](#) or in individual/institutional github instances linked to the Polifonia Github.

The Research Ecosystem is at the same time both firm and agile. It is firm due the formal (machine-actionable) documentation of components (annotation scheme) and defined workflows for annotation and selection of certain research assets as components. It is agile, because the annotation scheme can be changed and the workflows of annotation, selection and validation can be adapted. An example for such an extension, is the work on licences. Information on licences was added as a metadata field after discussions around the first version of the DMP. In a recent deliverable (D2.6) [7] this work has been continued, from an analysis of the licences resources Polifonia uses come with, over an automatic validation of their machine-readability, to an enrichment of licence information of Polifonia components. In the course of the project, and coordinated by the Technical Board, the Polifonia Research Ecosystem has become the spin for all activities relevant for data management. The Polifonia Research System website has also been further updated. A user validation has been executed to test to which extend the navigation through the Polifonia research assets is enabled by the design of the website. The current second version has been enhanced by visual overview and by a possibility to search for Pilot related content.

1.3.2. Main elements of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem

The Polifonia Research Ecosystem (in short Research Ecosystem) contains elements of various nature. All of them have a formalised description (called annotations). The main element are **components** and **containers**. [Annotation Scheme overview](#).

At the heart of the Research Ecosystem are components. An Ecosystem component is any resource produced by or used during research. **Components** can be ordered in three large types: *Data*, *Tools*, and *Reports* (see Tab 1.3 for details).

What is an Ecosystem container? Components can be grouped in containers, representing a specific set of research activities (e.g. a subproject or task). In other words, **Containers** annotations contain information about the project organisation, such as:

- Project
- WorkingGroup
- WorkPackage
- Task
- UseCase
- Pilot

Component type	Description of the type	Subtypes
Data	The Research Ecosystem considers data any digital object that specifies, describes, or represents facts about the project's domain of interest.	Dataset, Repository, Registry, Ontology, Corpus, Lexicon, KnowledgeGraph, Schema
Tools	The Research Ecosystem considers tools any digital object that is being produced by the project to achieve a certain task computationally. We distinguish software from applications, whereby software is used (executed) by a user to perform the task; and applications are executable systems for the end-user to achieve a certain task computationally.	Application, WebSite, WebApplication, WebService, SPARQLEndpoint, MobileApp, CommandLineTool, Software, Workflow, API, UserInterface, DockerImageContainer, SoftwareLibrary, Notebook
Reports	The Research Ecosystem considers reports any digital object that specifies, describes, or represents facts about the project's domain of interest. Reports differ from Data as they are mainly directed to human consumption, rather than computational treatment.	Report, RequirementsCollection, Story, Persona, Mockup, Survey, InPresenceSurvey, FocusGroup, Documentation, Tutorial, EvaluationReport

Table 1.3: Research Ecosystem Components: Main and subtypes

There are two important points to emphasis

- Although the labels of the component types seem to be arbitrary, in the Research Ecosystem each of them is precisely defined.
- The types used are changing with the research process. They are in essence placeholders for types of activities and output which are emerging in the research process. At the end, some types might become discarded, others might be merged with other types.

By *precisely defined* we mean that there exist a glossary with all used terms, their function (as class, label) and their mutual relationship. So, although the above listed terms seems to be mundane, their meaning inside of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem is specified. Each of the elements (components and containers) has a specific set of metadata required to describe the components (and container). An overview of the schema can be found here: [Research Ecosystem Annotation Schema](#) (see also section 2.2 and Fig. 2.5).

1.3.3. The function of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem

The main aim of the Research Ecosystem is to formalise as much as possible those *research assets* which are most central to achieve the objectives of the project. The formal description enables an analysis of what are those corner stones, and at the same time it makes sure that those are documented in a clear way, enabling reproducibility and re-use of the Polifonia workflows and results.

Collective documentation is governed by the [Polifonia Ecosystem Development rulebook](#) which contains all guidelines, recommendations, and norms on how to contribute to the Polifonia Ecosystem. For each of the components one researcher or engineer (so-called *champion*) is defined, who is responsible for the documentation of a component. Various workshops (see Fig. 1.3) have been organised by the Technical Board to discuss, teach and execute the annotation process. In parallel, validation workflows are developed which test the completeness of annotation, and point to inconsistencies in the documentation. Last but not least, the <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/> (created by using content from the github) is designed in a way to enable an easy navigation through the Research Ecosystem components, and to see their mutual dependencies. In parallel with the

on-going development of the Research Ecosystem, also the Polifonia Research Ecosystem website is adapted to better serve needs of overview, monitoring and dissemination.

Figure 1.4: Overview about the main types of components in the Research Ecosystem

2. ORDP

The sections in this chapter follow the *Open Research Data Pilot* template, as introduced in 1.2.

2.1. Data Summary

The section *Data summary* describes the final data components which are at this time annotated in the Polifonia Ecosystem. By end of 2023, 29 components of the Research Ecosystem belong to the *Data* type. Figure 2.1 shows a snapshot of the overview from the [Polifonia Research Ecosystem Website](#) concerning the components type *Data*. The power of the Research Ecosystem unfolds, when navigating through the [Polifonia Ecosystem Website](#). Each of the listed components has a subsite in the Research Ecosystem website with a short summary and related components listed. Each component is also further hyperlinked to its github repository, which often entails additional information. The annotation scheme for each components can be also seen in github. What we present in this section of the DMP are visual overviews (snapshots of website and github sites), and a tabular overview of the 29 Data components. We take one component - The Bells Knowledge Graph - to illustrate how final data components in the Polifonia Research Ecosystem relate to the original inventory of data sources which we added to each of the DMP versions as an Appendix. All 29 data components are annotated according the Research Ecosystem Annotation scheme in Github. A version of them is also released in Zenodo. We expect further components to be added to the Research Ecosystem before of the end of the project.

To understand the *data* output of the Polifonia project, we list the specific subtypes which fall under the overall *Data* type, the definition of those types according to the Polifonia Research Ecosystem Annotation Scheme, and the (actual) components annotated in the table 2.1. Several class labels, such as Repository or Dataset are not yet further specified. Still, they have been introduced because the function of those 'data collections' have been different in the research process in Polifonia. In the further evaluation of all components, also the annotation schema itself will be inspected and some of those subclasses might be merged. The attentive reader will also see that the BELLS Knowledge Graph is currently listed under the subtype 'Repository'. This will be corrected in the next annotation and validation workshop. Not surprisingly for a project which heavily relies on semantic web technology, the majority of *Data* takes the form of ontologies and populated ontologies, so-called knowledge graphs. Those are data produced in the project.

EXAMPLE: Bells Ontology The Polifonia Ecosystem Website lists a summary of the Bells Ontology (see Fig. 2.2). When clicking on the Metadata button, the whole of the annotations becomes visible (see Figures 2.3,2.4).

Scrolling through the metadata shows not only who produced this component, as part of which workpackage, but also explicitly notes on which other work it builds, which sources it reuses, and which licence it uses.

In the case of the Bells Ontology it becomes obvious that this ontology is a part of the overall Polifonia Ontology, while at the same time it also builds on an existing ontology which has been used for main source of the Bells pilot, namely the [Catalogo generale dei Beni Culturali](#). This catalog was already published as Linked Data, but has now been enriched due to the work of the Polifonia project. The question of sustaining the work of Polifonia beyond the horizon of this project is addressed by the collaboration with a Cultural Heritage provider. The ICCD (Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo e la Documentazione) has enhanced the search functionalities of the catalog. Such impact and sustainability of Polifonia results relying on the construction of the consortium itself, can be found in many pilots.

To enable a cross-check between the data components as they now appear in the Polifonia Ecosystem and the original overview table for all Pilots, we added an additional column in the table (see Appendix 1). Each pilot has also entry in the Polifonia Research Ecosystem, which makes it possible to check easily which of the data sources listed in the table are already components in the Ecosystem. Moreover, each pilot leader checked the updated

Data

This section collects project outputs that are released as *data*. The ecosystem considers data any digital object that specifies, describes, or represents facts about the project's domain of interest. These include various types of digital objects such as [datasets](#), [corpora](#), [ontologies](#), or [repositories](#).

Figure 2.1: Overview about all Data components

table once more. The example of the Bells Ontology shows the power of the formalisation of all research assets as components of an ecosystem, including of those of the type data.

Data subtype	Definition	List of components	#
Ontology	A formalised a set of concepts and categories in a specific domain or area	Bells Ontology; CoMeta Ontology; Music Instrument Ontology; MEETUPS Ontology; Music Meta; Polifonia Ontology Network (PON); Source ontology; Tunes Ontology	8
KnowledgeGraph	Machine-readable Data collections (Linked Data, API)	Broadcast Concerts Knowledge Graph; Listening Experience Database; Licences Knowledge Graph; MEETUPS Knowledge Graph; MusicBO Knowledge Graph; ChoCo Knowledge Graph; Harmony: the Harmonic Memory	7
Repository	Specific Data collections	BELLS Knowledge Graph; FoNN – Folk N-gram aNalysis; Root Note Detection; Local Harmonic Agreement based on Recurrent Patterns; Textual Corpus Population	5
Dataset	Specific Data collections	Documentary evidence benchmark; Patterns Knowledge Graph - Output datasets; musoW dataset; ChoCo Dataset	4
Corpus	Specific Data collection	Polifonia Corpus; Ceol Rince na hÉireann MIDI corpus; MEETUPS Corpus	3
Lexicon	Specific Data collection	Polifonia Lexicon - The Polifonia Multilingual WordNet	1
Schema	Specific Data collection	Ecosystem Component Annotation Schema	1

Table 2.1: Main data types in Polifonia

The screenshot shows the Polifonia website interface. On the left is a dark blue navigation sidebar with the Polifonia logo and a list of menu items: Home, Work packages (with a dropdown arrow), Pilots (with a dropdown arrow), Requirements, Data, Tools, Reports, Licences, Changelog, and Rulebook. The main content area has a light grey header with a search bar labeled 'Q Search' and a link 'Polifonia on Github'. Below the header is a blue button labeled 'Show Metadata'. The main heading is 'Bells Ontology', followed by a paragraph of text: 'The [Bells Ontology](#) makes it possible to describe bells, bell towers and bell ringers. Bells, which are the main subject of this module, are described by means of measurable, intrinsic aspects such as weight, materials, conservation status, as well as properties deriving from interpretation situations, such as authorship attribution, dating, execution techniques, and their related objects (e.g. bibliography). The Bell ontology modules reuses and extends the ArCo ontology network.'

Figure 2.2: Bell Ontology Summary on the Polifonia Ecosystem Website

Component id	https://w3id.org/polifonia/ontology/bells-ontology/
Type	Ontology
Name	Bells Ontology
Description	The Bell ontology represents concepts and relationships to describe bells, bell towers and bell ringers.
Image	https://github.com/polifonia-project/bells-ontology/blob/main/diagrams/bells.png
Work package	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP2
Pilot	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BELLS
Project	polifonia-project
Resource	ontology/bells.owl
Release date	15/04/2023
Release number	v1.0
Release link	https://github.com/polifonia-project/bells-ontology/blob/main/ontology/bells.owl

Figure 2.3: Annotation metadata for the Bells Ontology (1/2)

Doi	10.5281/zenodo.7919970
Changelog	https://github.com/polifonia-project/bells-ontology/tag/v1.0
Licence	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• CC-BY_v4
Copyright	Copyright (c) 2023 Valentina Carriero, Elena Musumeci, Fiorela Ciroku
Contributors	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Valentina Carriero• Elena Musumeci• Fiorela Ciroku

Figure 2.4: Annotation metadata for the Bells Ontology (2/2)

2.2. FAIR Data

2.2.1. ORDP questions about FAIR

The FAIR section is the heart of the ORDP. In the first DMP version, we raised awareness to the FAIR principles and took the pilots to discuss selected issues around FAIR. In the second DMP version, we used this section of the ORDP to detail all the Polifonia Guidelines (from general guidelines how to do open science to very specific check lists for software quality), which at the end contribute to the FAIRness of data. Eventually, the Polifonia Research Ecosystem is our main *instrument* or approach to ensure FAIRness. Having said this, in this third version we return to the original layout of the ORDP template and answer one to one the questions of the FAIR section, giving pointers to which part of the structure of the Research Ecosystem and/or the processes to design and fill the Ecosystem with content corresponds to the question asked.

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Are the data produced and/or used in the project discoverable with metadata, identifiable and locatable by means of a standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers)?

The project uses and produces data (see section 2.4). The [rulebook](#) for the Polifonia Research Ecosystem details when a component, including data components needs to be created and how it needs to be annotated. Components have internal identifier (on github), but versions of them are also released in Zenodo, these versions get a DOI.

What naming conventions do you follow?

According to the rulebook "Some naming conventions have been discussed. For instance, for github repositories avoid including "Polifonia" in the name (e.g. ecosystem rather than polifonia-ecosystem). Avoid acronyms (ontology-network instead of ON). For the ontologies and knowledge graph, as part of publishing of them as Linked Data [8], naming conventions are in place for the URLs." A [Guideline for ontology and knowledge graph development and documentation](#), as part of the rulebook details further steps.

Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

The annotation scheme does not contain a free text keywords field. Having said this, as all components can be found as github repositories, the free text search engine of github represents the 'google search' possibility. Who is interested in re-use need will probably first get acquainted with the Polifonia project. In general, findability of output is guaranteed by the decision which research assets are described as components in the Research Ecosystem and the Research Ecosystem Website, which with its facets enables to navigate through the output. More thoughts on how to increase re-usability can be found in the section 2.6.

Do you provide clear version numbers?

Yes. See as an example from the annotation scheme: release-date: 2023/01/18 release-number: v1.0-alpha release-link: <https://github.com/fabulous-inc/repo1/releases/tag/v0.8.1>

What metadata will be created? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

The [Annotation scheme](#) contains all metadata used for the components. The annotation schema is aligned to schema.org and the Ecosystem website include embedded Schema.org annotations, generated thanks to SPARQL Anything¹ [9].

Making data openly accessible

Which data produced and/or used in the project will be made openly available as the default? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restrictions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from voluntary restrictions.

The project follows the "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" rule. All data which can be open, are made open (see also section 2.5 for the issues of licences). As we work with data sources provided by (public funded) cultural heritage content providers, their rules for access (human and machine) to their sources is obliged.

How will the data be made accessible (e.g. by deposition in a repository)?

Based on the review in the Technical Board, components (including Data) will be regularly released as version into

¹<http://sparql-anything.cc>

```

Polifonia Ecosystem
Annotation Schema

---
component-id: fabulous-component-source-code
type: Software
name: The Fabulous Source Code
description: Source code of The Fabulous
logo: https://www.example.org/logo.png
work-package:
- WP1
- WP2
pilot:
- ThePilot
project: a-fabulous-project
resource: https://github.com/fabulous-inc/repol/releases
demo: https://www.example.org/fabulous/demo
release-date: 2023/01/18
release-number: v1.0-alpha
release-link: https://github.com/fabulous-
inc/repol/releases/tag/v0.8.1
doi: 10.5281/zenodo.000000
changelog: https://github.com/fabulous-
inc/repol/releases/tag/v0.8.1
licence:
- Apache-2.0
copyright: "Copyright (c) 2023 Fabulous, Inc"
contributors:
- A developer <http://www.example.org>
...

...
related-components:
- informed-by:
  - fabulous-requirements
- use-case:
  - fabulous-uc
- story:
  - fabulous-story
- persona:
  - fabulous-persona
- documentation:
  - fabulous-component-docs
  - fabulous-component-tutorials
- extends:
  - "A Java project Jena https://www.example.org"
- reuses:
  - "Apache Camel https://camel.apache.org/"
- generated-by:
  - The AI code generator http://www.my-software-factory.com
- evaluated-in:
  - fabulous-evaluation
credits: "This project has received funding from the Lorem Ipsum
Funder research and innovation programme under grant agreement
01234556."

---
# The Fabulous Component

Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit, sed do
 eiusmod tempor incididunt ut labore et dolore magna aliqua. Ut
 enim ad minim veniam, quis nostrud exercitation ullamco laboris
 nisi ut aliquip ex ea commodo consequat. Duis aute irure dolor in
 reprehenderit in voluptate velit esse cillum dolore eu fugiat
 nulla pariatur. Excepteur sint occaecat cupidatat non proident,
 sunt in culpa qui officia deserunt mollit anim id est laborum
    
```

Figure 2.5: Annotation metadata for a component

the Polifonia Zenodo community. As shown in 2.4 most of the deposits in Zenodo are open, but there are some with restricted access.

Example: Polifonia Corpus It is interesting to look into those restricted records more closely. They all belong to Research Ecosystem Component [Textual Corpus Population](#), which is of a component of the Data type, subtype Repository. The related Github instance is [Polifonia Corpus](#). The readme in this github repository explains why releases of this dataset in Zenodo are restricted. "The data of the module cannot be downloaded due to copyright issue. However, it is possible to reconstruct the corpus using the metadata provided in the previous section. Furthermore, the data processed and annotated can be accessed interrogating the corpus (how to interrogate the corpus is explained in a README.md file inside the interrogation folder of this repository)."². So, even in cases where data used in the research cannot be published as open data, because of copyright issues, Polifonia makes sure that the workflow with which the data are created is open - and so reproducible; that the metadata of the dataset are open; and gives contact information of the researchers behind for those who want to re-use either workflow or results.

What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The Polifonia Ecosystem intrinsically also includes tools. According to the [Polifonia Ecosystem Website](#) "The ecosystem considers software any digital object that is being produced by the project to achieve a certain task computationally. We distinguish software from applications, where software is used (executed) by a user to perform the task. These include various types of digital objects such as scripts, software libraries, workflows, or APIs. The ecosystem considers applications executable systems and tools produced by the project for the end-user to achieve a certain task computationally. We distinguish applications from software, where software can be copied, moved, and executed in multiple different applications (each in relation to some usage scenarios). Applications include various types

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Corpus>

of artifacts such as Web Applications, Web sites, and Command Line Interface (CLI) tools". Most of components of type Tools are about applications related to creating ontologies and knowledge graphs, and tools to analyse the information published as a knowledge graph. The *Polifonia Portal*³, a website to interact with data and tools directly without the need to have a background in computer sciences, is also a component (of type Tool) in the Research Ecosystem.

Is documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

For the *Polifonia Portal* the user interacts with tools and data via a webinterface. There is documentation/help on how to navigate the Portal, and the Portal website design has been evaluated with potential users. For this component, users are not expected to interact with the code behind the portal. All other Tools components have a github instance, either inside of the Polifonia github repository (in the case they are developed in Polifonia) or in external github repositories (in case code is re-used from other projects). They all come with a documentation, which supports re-use. Additionally, Polifonia developed [Polifonia Software Guidelines](#) (based on good practices of software development), which has been applied for Tool components [2].

Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

As default all used software - of those tools which are central and though form a component in the Polifonia Ecosystem - is shared via github.

Where will the data and associated metadata, documentation and code be deposited? Preference should be given to certified repositories which support open access where possible.

As determined in the Polifonia Open Science Guidelines ([2]) all components of the Research Ecosystem (Data, Tools, and Reports) will be released to the Zenodo.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository?

Polifonia has created a Zenodo community, and submission to this community are moderated (via Workpackage 6).

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided?

No restrictions on use.

Is there a need for a data access committee? No. The Polifonia Technical Board takes care of possible questions.

Are there well described conditions for access (i.e. a machine readable license)?

License information is part of the Annotation scheme for each component (see also section 2.5).

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Not applicable

Making data interoperable

Are the data produced in the project interoperable, that is allowing data exchange and re-use between researchers, institutions, organisations, countries, etc. (i.e. adhering to standards for formats, as much as possible compliant with available (open) software applications, and in particular facilitating re-combinations with different datasets from different origins)?

Yes. As Polifonia uses Linked Data approaches and semantic web standards as technological backbone of the project, a large part of data is published as knowledge graphs (Type Data, subtype Knowledge Graph (see Table 2.1), with an API (provided via the Polifonia server at the University of Bologna). Those are machine-readable.

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable? Will you be using standard vocabularies for all data types present in your data set, to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability?

Yes. In the development of the Polifonia Ontology Network, other existing ontologies in the field of musicology, information retrieval, and cultural heritage were inspected and reused either directly or indirectly⁴ (see [Polifonia Ontology Network](#) and [10]). The deliverable *D2.2: Ontologies and knowledge graphs of music objects, patterns, and software package – 2nd version (V1.0)* (currently under approval) reports in detail on those efforts. The Figure 2.6 gives a schematic overview of the ontologies developed in Polifonia, and on which ontologies we rely. Those are listed above

³still under development

⁴Direct reuse requires importing ontologies or part of them (e.g. individual entities, relations) and introduces a dependency to any possible changes and availability. In indirect reuse, relevant entities and patterns from other ontologies are used as templates (replicated and extended) while being aligned to ensure interoperability.

of the block "PON Core" and include among others such as ArCo, DOREMUS, Music Ontology, MusicTheory, MusicOwl and so forth. Among these, only ArCo has been directly reused, given the active involvement and synergies of our development team.

Figure 2.4: Overview of the main modules in the Polifonia Ontology Network, with Polifonia's pilots as early adopters (grey circles). Foundational models (Source, Instrument, Music Meta, Music Representation) provide the backbone of PON, built on top of the Core module while leveraging the main ontologies reused directly or indirectly.

Figure 2.6: Overview of modules in the Polifonia Ontology Network.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies?

Research projects have the aim to extend the boundaries of what has been thought prior by default. As a consequence, they have a tendency to expand or fundamentally change existing ontologies [11]. Polifonia is no exception to this. Having said this Polifonia took utmost care to re-use existing ontologies (see Figure 2.6).

Increase data re-use (through clarifying licences)

See section 2.5.

How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible?

Polifonia in its Open Science Guidelines (see Appendix 2) encourages Open Access policies, this includes the use of licences from the CC-BY family, and promote commercial-friendly licenses for software (e.g. Apache 2.0) (see also section 2.5).

When will the data be made available for re-use? If an embargo is sought to give time to publish or seek patents, specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

As data are open by default as part of the Ecosystem, no embargo is needed.

Are the data produced and/or used in the project useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project? If the re-use of some data is restricted, explain why.

Yes, all output of Polifonia, which is annotated in the Research Ecosystem is available for other parties to be re-used.

How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Depending to the preservation policies in Zenodo and Github we assume for at least some decades.

Are data quality assurance processes described?

Yes, each component of the Polifonia Ecosystem, including components of the type Data, is evaluated by the Technical Board. In addition, annotators could rely on a Web based user interface to verify the content during the annotation workshops⁵ Prior to listing in the Ecosystem, the annotations are automatically checked for validity by a [Python-based validator](#). Bibliographic references, links to source material are among the required metadata fields. All of the Data components are also discussed in other forms of output, such as Deliverables. If provided by a Cultural Heritage institution, there data curation principles (including quality check) are applied.

2.2.2. FAIR as a process

The FAIR section of the ORDP takes FAIR as a feature to which certain research objects, primarily data, have to adhere. But FAIRification, as it is sometimes called, concerns the process to make data FAIR, so it is dynamic. Its implementation is further domain specific as research on FAIR implementation shows [12].

Polifonia responded to the need to raise awareness to FAIR in all phases of the research process, by adapting the template for Deliverables.

With the preparation of the DMP version 2 2022 we introduced a new section in the deliverable template, called *FAIR section*. It was made obligatory for each DL to share thoughts on the FAIRness of data and processes in a free text form. The resulting sections were data-mined for the DMP version 2 and reported there [2]. With the Polifonia Ecosystem reaching more maturity, the *FAIR section* was re-designed in 2023, from a free text, to an actual check list (see below). The idea to have an additional FAIR section obligatory for each deliverable, and the change formatting this section from free text to check list, illustrate what we mean by 'FAIR as a process'. While for semantic web projects, FAIR is part of the design process - as this methodology roots in machine actions and standards, how to ensure that this FAIRness is also visible in all documentation still requires an effort. The whole Research Ecosystem approach aims to make research components FAIR. Very concretely, the re-design of the FAIR section in the DL template supported the process of identifying relevant components for the Polifonia Research Ecosystem and led to richer annotations of submitted components.

Compliance to the FAIR principles - new DL section This (new) section in the Deliverable (DL) template encompasses information which helps the knowledge management in the project and to make Polifonia FAIR (operating according to principles of Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable).

List all components related to this DL: use the component type classification of the Ecosystem (even if a specific component is not or not yet part of the Ecosystem)

Types (consult the [Annotation Scheme](#) for the actual lists of types/suptyes used for containers and components)

- Data
- Tools
- Reports

For each container/component please answer the questions in the list below. It is also possible to group components if the answers are the same.

Component XYZ – Type ABC

⁵The ecosystem toolkit will be further described in *D5.7 - Tool support for citing and annotating musical scholarly objects*

- Does the component adhere to the Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science? If Yes, list the rules you specifically applied R1,R2, ...R10? (see D7.2 DMP version 2 , p20, for the 10 Rules, [2])
- Provide the link to the component as part of the Polifonia Github organisation repo. If you don't have one, create it or provide a convincing motivation why not.
- Is the component is part of the Polifonia Research Ecosystem (Yes, Planned, Not applicable). If YES provide link to github
- Is the component already part of Zenodo? – If Yes provide link, if No, create a Zenodo component or provide a convincing motivation why you prefer not to have the component in Zenodo. (Follow the Zenodo upload guidelines, to be found here D7.2 DMP version 2)

For Ecosystem components check <https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook> and assess whether your component is compliant with it.

There are some specific questions for *semantic artefacts* such as Ontologies and Knowledge Graphs:

1. Is the component aligned with the Polifonia Ontology? (Yes/No) if no perform the alignment or provide a convincing motivation
2. Provide information about the Knowledge Graph hosting (and add it in table KnowledgeGraphProviders)
3. Assess whether the component is compliant with the Ontology/KGs guidelines. If no, motivates and describe your action plan to fix it

For software components: Assess whether your component obliges the Polifonia Software Deliverable Guidelines? (see DMP version 2 [2]) If no, motivate and describe your action plan to fix this.

2.3. Allocation of resources

What are the costs for making data FAIR in your project? How will these be covered? Note that costs related to open access to research data are eligible as part of the Horizon 2020 grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions). Who will be responsible for data management in your project? Are the resources for long term preservation discussed (costs and potential value, who decides and how what data will be kept and for how long)?

Polifonia allocated substantial resources (12 personmonths in total) to tasks of data stewardship. The Data Steward is part of WP7 (the overall project management), and participates in the *Technical Board*. Polifonia's workflows intrinsically focus on making data and tools machine actionable, so making data FAIR was covered by the project budget from the beginning. Additionally, the university of the coordinator Professor Valentina Presutti, the University of Bologna has committed resources to the hosting of webservices (as listed further below) also after the project.

As described above the whole Polifonia Research Ecosystem approach relies on the fact that **all** machine executable knowledge production is documented in the [Polifonia Github instance](#). This concerns not only activities leading to Tools (software and applications), but also Data and Reports.

The Polifonia Github instance encompasses 96 so-called repositories. "A repository is the most basic element of GitHub. It's a place where you can store your code, your files, and each file's revision history. Repositories can have multiple collaborators and can be either public or private." ⁶ The most used languages are Python, HTML, Jupyter Notebook, JavaScript and CSS. There further so-called external repositories, some of which are also harvested for the Research Ecosystem Components. The Polifonia Github instance knows 29 registered participants. The Github platform allows to monitor which repositories are most actively worked in. But, most important for the Research Ecosystem Approach is that content from GitHub is machine-readable and this way can be included in workflows, such as the ones on which the monitoring of components (including Data relies).

Tools components such as the Polifonia Web portal are also developed in the Polifonia Github repository⁷. The Polifonia Research Ecosystem itself is also part of the Polifonia Github instance.⁸

At the end of the project, the legacy of Polifonia will be comprised of the following parts:

⁶<https://docs.github.com/en/repositories/creating-and-managing-repositories/about-repositories>

⁷<https://github.com/polifonia-project/portal>

⁸<https://github.com/polifonia-project/ecosystem>

Figure 2.7: Overview of the Polifonia Github instance

- [Polifonia Project Website](#) Hosted by the University of Bologna, and maintained for five years after the project; regularly crawled by the Internet Archive, actual [Permalink 12.12.2023](#) contains an overview about the project organisation, and features selected output
- The Polifonia Portal (in development) Hosted by the University of Bologna, and maintained for 5 years after the project enables various users (from laypersons, layexperts to musicology scholars) to browse through content provided by the Polifonia pilots and to explore new ways to analyse musical cultural heritage.
- The [Polifonia Zenodo community](#) (see section 2.4)
- A set of API's hosted at the University of Bologna to access the Knowledge Graphs produced in Polifonia and maintained for five years after the project

2.4. Data security

What provisions are in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data)? Is the data safely stored in certified repositories for long term preservation and curation?

As the project does not deal with GDPR related or potentially harmful data, security risk assessment is at minimum level and does not require any particular form of encryption or data security assurance. Concerning aspects of long-term preservation, Polifonia decided to use Zenodo as public, open, long-term repository for its outputs. A [Polifonia community](#) has been created with guidelines how to submit (see DMP version 2 [2]). The content of the Polifonia Zenodo community is curated via Workpackage 6.

By end of 2023, in total 97 records were submitted to Zenodo, of which 82 are open access, and 15 are restricted access. The latter require a mail action to ask for access.

Zenodo content types	#
Dataset	57
Publication	31
Software	6
Presentations	6

Table 2.2: Polifonia Zenodo Community

2.5. Ethical and legal aspects

Are there any ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

Polifonia does not collect personal data as research data. But, the source data Polifonia uses often have specific conditions of (re)-use, expressed in licences and copyright statements. The example of the Polifonia Corpus given in the subsection above illustrates the difficulties of data re-use. But, for machine executable actions on data, the problem is even larger. For machine actions to be able to respect access conditions, licences need to be formalised in a machine-readable way. Licences and copyright statement as such are already formal expressions, and standardised. But, when added as metadata to a certain dataset, the textual (string) expression can take different forms. Polifonia devoted a whole deliverable (DL D2.6: Ontology of licencing, ownership and conditions of use (V1.0), submitted October 2023) to this problem. ([7]). We summarise here some of the main findings of this deliverable.

The executive summary ([7]) states " There are various issues when it comes to licences:

- there is a large variety of licences and copyright statements used in the domain of musical content
- the information about licences is not always added to metadata or not added in a standardised way, but often 'hidden' in plain text on websites
- licences regulating the access to and use of a webservices (e.g., repositories) and licences regulating the access and use of content provided via webservices (e.g. datasets in a repository) are kind of entangled - there might be various, sometimes contradicting each other, licence information available for a certain data collection.

"

In this deliverable, we in particular analysed the content of the musoW a catalogue in which all main data components used by Polifonia are registered. musoW, music data on the web, is a Linked Open Data registry of music resources available on the web. It includes extensive descriptions of more than 500 music collections, datasets, digital libraries and software solutions relevant to music. In the Polifonia Research Ecosystem musoW appears as a component of type Tool, subtype Interface.⁹ A dumb of the metadata of this registry are also available as a component of type Data, subtype Dataset.¹⁰

As said before, the licence statement are usual not formalised in a machine readable way. Polifonia used the W3C Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL) as the reference representation method for computational licences. To support querying and reasoning over terms and conditions of licences, we also selected the DALICC collection of licences expressed as RDF/ODRL. The analysis of the musoW data showed which kind of statement are mostly used, namely 'Open Access' (third column). The table 2.3 also shows to which machine-readable ontology class (computational licence) these statements can be match (first column).

To summarise: Polifonia has addressed the licence issue proactively and as part of its research journey. We made inventories of licences used in pilots (and in the whole domain) (see for an overview DMP Version 2, appendix licences [2]). We developed automated methods to detect licence information (in metadata and on websites). We created a [Licences Knowledge Graph](#) as an important component in the Polifonia Research Ecosystem, of type

⁹https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/polifonia-project/registry_app/ecosystem/interface.html

¹⁰https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/polifonia-project/registry_app/ecosystem/dataset.html

Table 2.3: Summary of licence annotations in the musoW dataset - reproduced from DL2.6

https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/open-access	Open Access	274
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/cc-by	CC-BY	50
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/not-specified	Not specified	45
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/copyright	Copyright	30
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/unknown-licence	Unknown	29
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/cc0	CC0	26
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/cc-by-nc-sa	CC-BY-NC-SA	14
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/cc-by-nc	CC-BY-NC	9
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/gnu-gpl	GNU-GPL	5
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/privative	Privative	4
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/cc-by-sa	CC-BY-SA	3
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/mit-license	MIT License	2
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/cc-by-3.0	CC BY 3.0	2
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/gnu-fdl	GNU-FDL	1
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/cc-by-4.0	CC-BY 4.0	1
https://w3id.org/musow/vocab/cc-by-nc-nd	CC-BY-NC-ND	1

Data, and suptype Knowledge Graph. This way, Polifonia contributes to the ongoing scientific discourse around *computational licences*.

2.6. Other aspects - Reusability

In this section we detail another of our targeted approaches to foster the FAIRness of our data and workflows. During the Bologna meeting October 2023, we extensively discussed the various impacts our project might have: scientific/academic impacts and socio-economic impacts. Due to the topic of the project, even citizens and society at large can have interest in reusing the project outputs. Re-usability is a necessary (pre)condition to foster impact. In a brainstorm session we devised a matrix of important aspects when it comes to re-usability. Re-usability can mean different things. For **Data** increasing FAIR aspects, such as machine-executability but also richer metadata are part of re-usability. If it comes to **Tools** (Software and application) good code documentation according to standards for software sustainability are important. For other **Tools** such as user interfaces, extended user tests, good web design and good help information are important. To some extent, the cross-links documented in the annotations of components are a first indication that relevant Polifonia output is re-used **inside** of the project consortium. But, in the light of sustainability and open (reproducible) science, our aspirations are higher. We have designed a survey, which will be executed at the beginning of 2024, and which structure is listed below. The results of the survey will be analysed in the upcoming D1.8.

2.6.1. Survey on Re-usability

1. What is the name of your Polifonia project or component? (If you have more than one, even if they are related, you may wish to fill in the survey once for each.) Required to answer. Single line text. Enter your answer

2. If there is a GitHub repository of the component/project, please add it here Single line text. Enter your answer

3. Please include the Ecosystem id of either the component or the container (if more components) Single line text. Enter your answer

4. Which of these best describes your project type? Required to answer. Single choice. Software Data Knowledge graph, ontology, or similar User interface Other

5. Who is the target audience for your project? Eg developers, or only Polifonia developers; musicologists; historians; etc. Required to answer. Multiple choice. Developers (in the project team) Developers (any) Domain Experts Computational Musicologists Musicologists Historians Researchers Other

6. How reusable is your project in the following five aspects? When considering your breadth of project goals: if the project goals are highly specific to you (e.g. software not reusable because it is one-off curatorial work), and would not be of interest to others, this makes it less reusable. If the project goals address the goals of a broad class of users/tasks, this makes it more reusable.

When considering its reusability with respect to technical knowledge: if the user would need substantial, specific technical knowledge to reuse it, this makes it less reusable. Example: expertise in coding in C. If they would need to visit your lab or call you to get started, this makes it less reusable. If the project provides good "getting started" documentation, this makes it more reusable.

When considering its reusability with respect to domain knowledge: if the user would need substantial, specific domain knowledge to reuse it, this makes it less reusable. Example: expertise in musicology of 16th century Italian folk music.

When considering its reusability with respect to computational resources: if the user would need substantial, specific computational resources to reuse it, this makes it less reusable. Examples: requirement for a server with large RAM, a GPU, or web hosting.

When considering its customisability: if the project can be easily extended, customised, or re-branded, this makes it more reusable.

For the following statements, higher is better (more reusable). Required to answer. Likert.

7. Has your project already been reused by someone other than its core developers (ie, you or your group)? Even if that reuse is not "complete", please include it. Required to answer. Single choice. No Yes, reused within Polifonia Yes, reused outside Polifonia

8. Please state the technical knowledge requirements as a list of comma-separated standards, languages (e.g.: "XML, RDF, Python, Java, SPARQL") Required to answer. Single line text. Enter your answer

9. Specify what type and amount of formats the project deals with? Required to answer. Multiple choice. Custom, ad-hoc input formats Well-known / standard input formats (e.g. JSON, CSV, RDF, MusicXML, Excel, ...) Single format Multiple formats

10. How much the project/component is able to tolerate or provide support for dealing with imperfect, incomplete, or low-quality data? Required to answer. Single choice. Data completeness/quality affects the system substantially Requires a format but can handle incomplete data Deals with fully unstructured data (e.g. texts or images) The question doesn't apply to this component

11. If you would like to give any comments to expand on your answers above, please enter them here. Eg, if you have constraints on data formats or computational requirements which are not captured by previous questions. Multi Line Text. Enter your answer

12. What is the approximate Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of your project? Higher TRL means closer to being in real-world use.

See https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Technology_readiness_level. We will use the EU definition:

TRL 1 – basic principles observed TRL 2 – technology concept formulated TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
TRL 4 – technology validated in lab TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies) TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies) TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment TRL 8 – system complete and qualified TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space) Required to answer.
Rating. 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

13. What are your exploitation and reuse strategies? (Choose zero or more.) Required to answer. Multiple choice.

- Publicise via academic venues
- Publicise via social media
- Educate others in the use of the project
- Use the project in education
- Live services, eg a webapp maintained by you
- Third-party companies offer software-as-a-service
- Deposit or index the data in well-known repositories
- Via GitHub - no commitment to maintenance or support
- Via GitHub - we have a commitment to maintain and support the project
- Via GitHub - a community maintains the software and provides support

14. If your project is of type Data/Schema, please choose which type(s) of reuse are possible Multiple choice.

- Reuse in a similar domain
- Reuse in a similar task
- Reuse to produce new data conforming to same schema
- Other

15. If your project is of type Software, please choose which type(s) of reuse are possible :Multiple choice.

- Reuse by changing the input data
- Reuse by configuring it to produce different data
- Other

16. Is your project/component domain independent? Single choice. Yes No (e.g. it is specific to Music)

17. How much the data or software can be extended? Single choice. Not at all It can be It is supposed to

18. If your project is of type User Interface, please choose which type(s) of reuse are possible :Multiple choice. Reusable with different data Customisable with look and feel, and branding Other

19. Please give your name so that we can contact you in case we need to clarify any responses. Single line text. Enter your answer

3. Conclusions

The DMP closes with a short Conclusion section summarising the lessons learned and measures taken to transfer the Ecosystem approach to other collaborative settings.

The main and most tangible outcome of the Data Management Planning in Polifonia is the **Polifonia Research Ecosystem**. Earlier versions of the Data Management Plan reported about the design for the Research Ecosystem and first steps of its implementation. Now, that the Polifonia Research Ecosystem is populated with components, this DMP version describes Data components and other types of components as they are curated via the Ecosystem.

The Polifonia Ecosystem represents

- a conceptual framework [6]
- an implementation in Github with (a schema, a rulebook, and workflows)
- a website to navigate its content (archived in the Internet Archive)
- its components have long-term legacy in the Polifonia Zenodo community

Until the end of the project, we will continue to work on adapting the Research Ecosystem. We will describe the scientific background for all technical aspects in detail in deliverable 5.7: *Tool support for citing and annotating musical scholarly objects*.

But, our aspirations go further. We will scientifically discuss and practically test the transfer-ability of the Research Ecosystem to other projects. For us, the Research Ecosystem as developed in Polifonia constitutes a machine-actionable Data Management Plan which goes beyond data as research assets. With the Research Ecosystem approach, Data Management becomes part of the overall research assets management (assets called Ecosystem components). This way Data are managed in context, and in connections to Tools (which constitutes the methodological side in research), and Reports (which constitutes the bibliographical, documentation side of research). We will further investigate connections to other similar new metadata schemes as RO_CRATE, or the FAIR_Implementation Profiles [12].

Lessons learned

1. Each DMP starts with some kind of tabular overview. Often a row is representing a 'data asset' which can be a collection, a dataset, To describe this data asset (with column headers) one can consult various metadata scheme: from generic ORDP, over bibliographic (Dublin Core), to domain specific scheme's. Give you 'data assets' an identifier! Plan for interview-setting and an iterative process.
The annotation scheme of the Research Ecosystem gives an example which main fields to use, and how in those fields to connect to other controlled vocabularies and schemes
2. The DMP is often seen as an activity at one point in time, but research is a process, and so is the management of data in this process. Prepare yourself for changes! Conduct the DMP as an iterative process! Funding agencies can encourage or even require to have versions of DMP's, this way supporting iterative cycles and to foster the use of DMP as part of project management.
The implementation of a Research Ecosystem and its population sets a clear boundary condition, a clear way to trace research components, their change over time, their status, preservation and so on.
3. Determine a 'Data Steward' for your project. You are in a pole position when you have Library and Information Science expertise in your consortium, otherwise reach out to Working groups on Research Data Management as they exist in the [Research Data Alliance](#) and in many European Research Infrastructure consortia. Train your 'Data Steward', let them interact with existing infrastructure projects on FAIR and other important topics.

4. For projects with a strong computer engineering component, working on a shared platform is definitely a plus. GitHub is among the most popular platform, although it is a commercial service, there are contingency plans in terms service conditions change. In particular, the possibility to release github results in a version controlled way to Zenodo (which is a public service) makes github very attractive.
The Research Ecosystem represents a holistic methodology to conduct computer engineering driven interdisciplinary project.

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A. Overview of the main sources used in the pilots

In this Appendix, we include a Table with a description of the information sources provided by Pilot leaders.

Appendix 1: A

(updated September 2022, additions columns, rows, content are colour coded in red)

(updated October 2022, in connection to the Polifonia Ecosystem <https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/v2.0>)

Pilots	Source (meaning where data are coming from)	Link/reference to the source	File size	Metadata model/formats ¹⁴	Metadata standards ¹⁵	File format(s) ¹⁵	Access rights	Licence/copyrights	API ³⁶	Polifonia Ecosystem integration
1	BELES			XML + RDF	ArCo ICCD Vocabulary for Musical Instruments ICCD Vocabulary for Intangible Heritage	JPEG, TIFF, XML, RDF, HTML, MP3, MP4		now updated: CC BY 4.0	API SPARQL (customizable query). For photographs we have API IIIF (International Image Interoperability Framework)	<p>BELLS</p> <p>Analyse the bell heritage to the wider context of a landscape and cultural heritage</p> <p>Bell structures are widespread both in urban and rural areas. They contribute to the distinctive shape of a landscape, defining its soundscape and playing as markers of daily, festive and ritual times. Bell heritage is complex and fascinating and influences our perception of the places we live daily. Both its tangible and intangible assets, and their dependencies are hardly encoded explicitly: most of this heritage is transmitted orally. This pilot intends to encode this valuable</p>

	2	ORGANS	Het Historische Orgel in Nederland and (1997-2010)	https://vu.on.worldcat.org/oclc/782207831	60 MB	Theses of organs terminology exist	Possible connection to KOS for musical instruments. Probably, design one specifically for texts about (historical) pipe organs.	doc, docx, WPs	restricted	copy right NIV O ³⁸	<p>https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/pages/pilots/organs.html</p> <h2>ORGANS</h2> <p>Reconnect information on the histories and characteristics of historic organs in the Netherlands.</p> <p>The history of pipe organs is rich and diverse, and highly interrelated to economic, religious and artistic contexts. Currently, the information about building practices and characteristics of ~2000 Dutch pipe organs is only retrievable by manually paging a 15 volumes (4,500+ pages) encyclopedia: the Orgelencyclopedie (1997-2010). This pilot will extract a knowledge graph out of the text of the Orgelencyclopedie, which will provide digital (and quick) access to such huge and detailed knowledge, including connection to data about aspects of their wider historic contexts.</p> <p>Components: Ontology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Music Instrument Ontology • Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) <p>Documentation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ontology and knowledge graph development and documentation guidelines <p>The link https://vu.on.worldcat.org/oclc/782207831 leads to a bibliographic reference; it is not mentioned in one of the Polifonia components</p>	not yet, but exploration of hosting with third parties such as Muziekweb (national audio archive - all music (CDs) issued on Dutch market)	- Muziekbibliotheek van de omroep (National Broadcast Music Library)	to be integrated into Portal	see above	private	html, ttf	PON+	PON	11.5 MB	https://github.com/polifonia-project/organs-dataset	LOD publication	ORGANS	The github repository is there, but it is not linked to the PILOT in the Polifonia ecosystem yet
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3	FACETS	Neuma digital library	http://neuma.humanum.fr/		MIDI ontology? envisione d: PON	MIDI, MusicXML, MEI, ly, png, pdf	registered users /open	Yes, fully, through a REST API. http://neuma.humanum.fr/home/services	<p>https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/pages/pilots/facets.html</p> <p>FACETS</p> <p>Exploration and discovery in large collections of music scores through statistical features.</p> <p>Music libraries currently lacks well-founded information retrieval tools. While it is relatively easy to find music based on metadata, content-based music retrieval still remains as a challenge. The Facets pilot aims to tackle this challenge by building a faceted search engine (FSE) for large collections of music documents.</p> <p>In the course of Polifonia, the original search engine has been further developed.</p> <p>But, the Pilot also contributed to other components, such as the MusicMetaOntology</p> <p>https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/polifonia-project/music-meta-ontology/assets/ecosystem/mela_ontology_header.html</p> <p>And the overall Polifonia Ontology https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/polifonia-project/ontology-network/header.html</p> <p>At the end this source was not used in the project.</p>
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	e (Port collecti ons)				TXT, MIDI, File mak er, CSV, XML	Various annotation standards reconciled with the Music Meta ontology	RDF, RDFS, OWL, KERN, MIDI, TXT, JSON, , XML, ABC, MEI, SQL-databases, CSV, TSV, HTML, HARM, JSON, JAMS, etc.			https://polifonia-disi.uniibo.it/choco/	<p>INTERLINK</p> <p>Interlinking of collections in European digital music libraries and audiovisuals archives.</p> <p>In order to answer research questions, musical heritage scholars need to combine diverse datasets ranging from music scores, audiovisual material to metadata. They need to identify similar entities and concepts implicitly present in the data, across different collections in different institutions.</p> <p>Components:</p> <p>Ontology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CoMeta Ontology • Music Instrument Ontology • Music Meta • Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) <p>Repository</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Harmonic Agreement based on Recurrent Patterns <p>Software</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pymusicmeta • Harmony: the Harmonic Memory <p>And more see Ecosystem website</p>
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I N T E R L I N K

4	I N T E R L I N K	Dutch Song Data base	www.liederenbank.nl	630 MB	File mak er Data base	Filemaker Database	open	https://www.meeuwen.nl/over-hel-meeuwen-s-instituut/wil/discipliner	no	See PILOT TUNES	This pilot integrates a lot of sources from other Pilots, it contributed also substantially to the Polifonia ontology engineering (see the four above listed ontology components).
		MTC- FS- INST- 2.0	www.liederenbank.nl/mtc	1.3 GB	csv	**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY- NC- SA 3.0	no	See PILOT TUNES	
		MTC- ANIN- 2.0.1	www.liederenbank.nl/mtc	84 MB	csv	**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY- NC- SA 3.0	no	See PILOT TUNES	
		Melodi c Featur es for Meerte ns	https://zenodo.org/record/3551003	81.6 MB	N/A	json	open	CC BY- NC-	no		

	T U N E S	Dutch Song Data- base	www.liederenbank.nl	630 MB	File mak- er Data base		Filemaker Database,	open	https://www.liederenbank.nl/cm/snl/over/het-mee-rten-s-insitt-juul/discipliner	no	<p>Components: Ontology</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Music Meta • Polifonia Ontology Network (PON) • Tunes Ontology <p>And many other tools</p>
7		MTC- FS- INST- 2.0	www.liederenbank.nl/mt	1.3 GB	csv		**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY- NC- SA 3.0	no	To be checked

MTC-ANIN-2.0.1	www.liederenbank.nl/mtc	84 MB	csv		**kern, midi, pdf, txt, lilypond source	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no	
Meeloes for Meerte									
Tune Collections and ESSEN Folkso	https://zenodo.org/record/3551003	81.6 MB	N/A		json	open	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0	no	To be checked
Neuma digital library	http://neuma.humanum.it/				MusicXML, MEI, ly, png, pdf	registered users		yes	See PILOT FACETS
Irish Traditional Music Archive (Porte)	http://port.irma.ie/welc								See PILOT FACETS
RISM Catalog of Musical Sources	https://rism.info	6.4 GB	XML		MARC-XML, RDF	open	CC BY	no	

8	T O N A L I T I E S	Lost Voices project Marenzio Online Tasso in Music Project Solo voices CPDL	.ac.uk/resources/786ad0983e6d233ab464e9cc6794160b http://www.solovoces.com/es https://www.cpd.org/wiki/index.php/Help:What_copyright_rules_apply_to_CPDL_scores%3F							Software • pymusicmeta Documentation • Ontology and knowledge graph development and documentation guidelines Story • Conflicting theoretical interpretations • Conflicting analytical annotations RequirementsCollection • Tonalties mockup
			http://neuma.humanum.fr/		MusicXML, MEI, ly, png, pdf	registered users	yes	See PILOT FACETS		
		Dutch Song Database	www.liederenbank.nl	File maker Database	File maker Database	open	no	See PILOT TUNES		

10	MEETUPS	Wikipedia	https://www.wikipedia.org/ https://github.com/polifonia-project/meetups_corpus_collection	266.1 MB	PON	RDF, TTL, N-quads, text	open	CC-BY-v4	https://polifonia.kmi.open.ac.uk/meetups/spardl/	https://polifonia-project.github.io/ecosystem/pages/bitots/meetups.html MEETUPS Providing a Web tool that enables the exploration and visualization of encounters between people in the musical world in Europe. This pilot focuses on supporting music historians and teachers by providing a Web tool that enables the exploration and visualisation of encounters between people in the musical world in Europe from c.1800 to c.1945, relying on information extracted from public domain books such as biographies, memoirs and travel writing, and open-access databases. Components: SPARQLEndpoint <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Open Knowledge Graph (OKG) KnowledgeGraph Listening Experience Database MEETUPS Knowledge Graph And other tools	NA
		Internet	https://archive.org								

B. Polifonia 10 Rules for Open Science

In this Appendix, we report the document of the Polifonia DM working group.

POLIFONIA 10 RULES for Open Science

[working document, first version published as Appendix of the DMP version 2, 2022]

Preamble

The process of research is sometimes described as a pipeline containing INPUT – the Research process itself – and OUTPUT. Although, this is just a very simple model and in practice the processes are much more circular [1] and messy [2], it can help to organise the documentation process.

Definitions

INPUT= all preconditions of research such as instruments/servers/..., institutions, funds and staff involved

PROCESS BOX = all research processes

OUTPUT = all tangible output such as Publications, but also Presentations, Proceedings papers, certain software packages etc.

Please note that ‘data’ [4] can appear in all of the phases: collections we use as source material (Input), datasets/ontologies we produce as part of the research process and publish for possible re-use, and data collections enriched which are hosted and possibly archive for the mid and long-term.

In the digital age, all three phases can be better traced and borders between the three phases also become blurry. In particular, more of the actual research process can be recorded and possibly also archived. [3] So, the Process Box – formerly perceived as a black box becomes much more visible, and intermediate results become objects worth to be documented too (think here of workflows, survey design and so on). Polifonia is embracing these possibilities while adhering to the principles of Open Science, Open Access and Fairness.

This document “Polifonia’s 10 Rules for open science”, contains guidelines for proper bibliographic referencing across all three platforms, which also apply to other platforms Polifonia consortium members might want or need to use for their own personal or institutional research information management (think here of your personal website, or

Research Information Systems your university uses). By this 10 Rules, Polifonia obliges the requirements to Open Access as defined in the Grant Agreement [5] (see also Appendix/or DMP v2)

This document function as a checklist and it an appendix to the Data Management Plan version 2, which in itself explains in greater detail documentation workflows in Polifonia.

POLIFONIA's 10 Rules of Open Science

R1: Polifonia requires that all essential components of the Polifonia Ecosystem are registered in the Polifonia github community.

Use the Polifonia GitHub for your code production, and document everything which is a component of the Polifonia Ecosystem according to the rulebook, so that your steps are transparent and reproducible!

The Ecosystem entails “anything that is not a research paper, dissemination product (e.g., video presentation of a tool), or deliverable “. The [Rulebook](#) contains “Guidelines, recommendations, and norms on how to contribute to the Polifonia Ecosystem”. defines what, when and how components to the Ecosystem. It defines a [schema](#) how to annotate components. Regularly, by the Technical Board from the Polifonia Ecosystem releases are selected for a machine executed submission to the Polifonia Zenodo community. Please note that the Rulebook is also a dynamical document. The Technical Board of Polifonia supervised the documentation process, and makes decision what in which form should be integrated in, or linked to the Polifonia Portal.

Cross-check with [Software-Delivery-requirements](#). [6]

R2: Polifonia recommends to use Zenodo, and other Open accessible platforms to register output.

Follow the **Upload guide** to the Polifonia Zenodo community. Please, register all items listed various [dissemination tables](#) (such as papers (preferably with preprints/author-version); presentations; and [deliverables](#) (reports).

R3: Polifonia Portal/Polifonia server

The Technical Board of Polifonia supervised the documentation process, and makes decision what in which form should be integrated in, or linked to the Polifonia Portal. University of Bologna (hosting the Polifonia server) produces an updated technical guide (as an internal document) how to use the Polifonia server for consortium members (external to the UB).

A working group “Knowledge graph providers” has set up, which defines requirements for LinkedData repositories (a type of Polifonia Ecosystem components, with an extended/minimum set of annotations) and their required documentation. These KOS service provisions are traced by using an internal [table](#),

R4: Use your ORCID to identify you as an author!

ORCID=PID for authors

PID enables machines to bring information together; ORCID allows you to register also other Author PID you might have, such as a SCOPUS ID; it has become a standard.

You can register your ORCID personally - sometimes institutions register their employees. if you not have one yet - register today. <https://orcid.org> Many other platforms ask you for your ORCID (Zenodo, or Conference organisers). The more you use it, the more of your content is marked with a specific, authoritative identifier.

R5: Acknowledge the grant (the Polifonia project) with each output!

This way the Polifonia project remains visible, and all output ever produced under the project is marked.

Use the standard sentence “*This work has been (partly) enabled by the H2020 Project Polifonia: a digital harmoniser for musical heritage knowledge funded by the European Commission Grant number 101004746*”. Use an acknowledgement section for it. Be aware that you can mention different grants in one acknowledgement, acknowledging numerous funding sources.

Be also aware that the Polifonia Grant number **101004746** is a PID too, this time provided by the European commission. So, in Zenodo for instance, you are required to add this in a specific field (see Zenodo

upload guide); also many journals ask you for that in their specific metadata schemes.

Content from Polifonia could be harvested in systems as OpenAire <https://explore.openaire.eu/search/find?active=projects&fv0=101004746&f0=q> and made visible.

R5: Use DOI's to refer to work you produce!

In short: a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) is a PID for a piece of 'work'. https://www.doi.org/registration_agencies.html DOI are used by publishers, but also Zenodo issues DOI's for content uploaded, and many (data) repositories do.

DOI is a PID for a whole bibliographic reference, while ORCID and GRANT# are PID's for part of the reference.

see <https://zenodo.org/record/5483727#.YWW9CS0RpWM> as an example

R6: For datasets you think are important cornerstones of your work, which you have listed as sources in the survey, deposit them (or pointers to them) into the Polifonia Ecosystem as GitHub (see R1).

You should also consider to archive 'authorative versions' into a certified data repository! Preferably a repository which is certified, issues a DOI, and offers version control.

Polifonia recommends the use of the Electronic Archiving System (DANS-KNAW) <https://easy.dans.knaw.nl/ui/home> and The Digital repository of Ireland <https://dri.ie/about-dri#>, both CoreTrustSeal certified. Polifonia also accepts any other repository which a community members might host/use mid it adheres to a certified standard.

Data Repositories which are also oblige to DataCite principles are listed here: <https://www.re3data.org>

For certified repositories see: <https://www.coretrustseal.org>

For European Archives check also:

<https://www.archivesportaleurope.net/home> Your archive could be there without your knowing ;-)

Familiarize yourself with data citation practices in your field, and cite research data accordingly!

R7: Authorship/publication Netiquette

Polifonia is a multidisciplinary project, where disciplines come with different norms/rules where, when and with whom to publish. Acknowledge collaboration always (depending on size and substance of a collaboration by co-authorship, or at least by an acknowledgement); Ask your group members in which form they would like to be acknowledged! Be alert to make also 'invisible work' (supporting work) visible too!

The Technical Board of Polifonia supervised the documentation process, and makes decision what in which form should be integrated in, or linked to the Polifonia Portal.

R8: Read guides prior to your data management!

Recommended: <https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Data-Management-Expert-Guide>; LCRDM: <https://www.lcrdm.nl/en/23things> and PARTHENOS guidelines: <https://zenodo.org/record/3368858#.YVcADC8Ro8Q>

Ask the DataManagers of your institutions and consult the DataStewards of Polifonia (DANS-KNAW)!

R9: List the licenses the sources you work with, and the products you produce adhere to.

Consult <https://www.openaire.eu/how-do-i-license-my-research-data> for general issues on data licensing. Inform yourself about licenses used in the musicology domain (see DMP version2, appendix x). If in doubt, ask the DataManagers of your institutions and consult the DataStewards of Polifonia (DANS-KNAW)!

R10: Adhere FAIR principles when producing semantic artifacts

- To publish sources as LOD read "Linked Open Data - 10 Things to reach the realm of LOD" - which is a popular 'translation' of the W3C recommendation <https://zenodo.org/record/3471806#.YWXCJi0RpWM>

- Inform yourself about state-of-art FAIR recommendations [see FAIRsFAIR on semantic artifacts <https://zenodo.org/record/5356630#.YWfxy0RpWM>. Those recommendations are generic, technology and domain agnostic but give an orientation.
- Test your objects! F-UJI tool <https://www.f-ujl.net> (With this tool you can test the FAIRness of anything which has an URL/PID/DOI!)
- Report your SPARQL endpoints to the Polifonia Portal, document sustainability strategies for machine-readable, life information produced!
- OWL use for PolifoniaKnowledge Graph (as described in DL's)
- For further practical tips for FAIR data management:
 - o LCRDM: <https://www.lcrdm.nl/en/23things>
 - o PARTHENOS guidelines: <https://zenodo.org/record/3368858#.YVcADC8Ro8Q>
 - o CESSDA guide: <https://www.cessda.eu/Training/Training-Resources/Library/Data-Management-Expert-Guide>
- Provide a persistent URI (PURL, DOI, w3id) for the resource (and related results)
- Provide a canonical citation associated with the resource
- Provide a licence specification (See creativecommons.org, opensource.org for more information)
- Indicate whether and where the resource is publicly available. For example as API, Linked Open Data, Download, Open Code Repository (the GitHub repo will work here).
- Make the resource publicly findable by registering it in (community) registries (e.g. Linked Open Vocabularies, BioPortal, or DataHub)? Indicate if and where it is registered in generic repositories such as FigShare, Zenodo or GitHub.
- Discuss your thought or plan for sustainability of the resource including the medium and long-term maintenance of the resource
- Indicate whether and which open standards the resource adopt (when applicable). Alternatively, motivate why it does not adopt standards.

References

- [1] D7.1. DMP v1
- [2] P. Wouters, K. Vann, A. Scharnhorst, M. Ratto, I. Hellsten, J. Fry, and A. Beaulieu (2008) Messy shapes of knowledge - STS explores informatization, new media, and academic work. The Virtual Knowledge Studio. In: The Handbook of Science and Technology Studies, edited by E. J. Hackett, O. Amsterdamska, M. Lynch and J. Wajcman. Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press. 319-352.
- [3] Van de Sompel, H., and Treloar, A. (2014) A Perspective on Archiving the Scholarly Web. Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Digital Preservation, iPres2014 ; [self-archived copy](#)
- [4] Borgman, book
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- [6] D3.3.

Appendix

Quotations from the GrantAgreement: [5]

“29.2 Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. In particular, it must:

(a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications;

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

(b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:

(i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or

(ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.

29.3 Open access to research data

Regarding the digital research data generated in the action ('data'), the beneficiaries must:
(a) deposit in a research data repository and take measures to make it possible for third parties to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate — free of charge for any user — the following:

(i) the data, including associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, as soon as possible;

(ii) not applicable;

(iii) other data, including associated metadata, as specified and within the deadlines laid down in the 'data management plan' (see Annex 1);

(b) provide information — via the repository — about tools and instruments at the disposal of the beneficiaries and necessary for validating the results (and — where possible — provide the tools and instruments themselves).

This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all of which still apply.

As an exception, the beneficiaries do not have to ensure open access to specific parts of their research data under Point (a)(i) and (iii), if the achievement of the action's main objective (as described in Annex 1) would be jeopardised by making those specific parts of the research data openly accessible. In this case, the data management plan must contain the reasons for not giving access.